

Detecting and mapping red clover (*Trifolium pratense*) using a fixed-wing drone equipped with a multispectral sensor

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1. Introduction and Justification

Latvian agricultural landscape is shaped by a complex interaction of biodiversity, economic, social, and political factors. The ongoing land-use changes, exacerbated by global climate change, are driving agrobiodiversity loss, which is crucial for food security as it underpins ecosystem services essential for agricultural productivity (Vasiliev, 2024). The Vidzeme Uplands, a typical region in central Latvia, have experienced significant transformations in landscape structure due to historical events. These changes have led to increased forest areas and altered land use patterns, impacting the ecological balance and agricultural practices (Nikodemus et al., 2005).

In this context, drone technology is becoming increasingly popular in agriculture for mapping and monitoring crops. These unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV) provide detailed and timely information that helps farmers make better decisions regarding crop management (Awais et al., 2023; Toscano et al., 2024). By integrating drone technology, Latvia can better monitor and manage its agricultural landscapes, ensuring sustainable practices supporting biodiversity and food security (Vasiliev, 2024). Through the LivingLab approach (Cascone et al., 2024), CODECS aims to co-develop, together with farmers and other related actors, user-friendly approaches, methods, and tools able to document the co-benefits and the costs of technologies applied to real contexts. Thus, the study reported in this document concerns a real-life co-development and demonstration of a drone-based tool to support rural actors in achieving sustainable goals regarding their productive outputs.

In this context, Latvian farmers are eligible, among other aspects, to receive support and environmental protection products to promote sustainable practices in certain crops, as part of the Common Agricultural Policy Strategic Plan for Latvia (Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Latvia, 2025). For nitrogen-fixing crops, for example, if leguminous plants constitute more than 50% of the sown mixture, the producers are eligible to receive financial subsidies. Incorporating this type of plants in forage mixtures is known to improve feeding quality (Kubkomawa, 2019), and, for this, mapping their distribution is crucial as it helps in understanding the distribution, quality and health of crops (Dlamini et al., 2024), aiding in efficient resource management and improving crop yield (McKenna et al., 2018).

Thus, based on the co-designed objectives for the application of drone mapping in a group of grasslands, this study focused on mapping red clover (*Trifolium pratense*) distribution using a fixed-wing drone equipped with a multispectral sensor and estimating its fractional coverage in each of the surveyed fields. In summary, drone images were processed to create reflectance maps, which allowed the calculation of vegetation indices. These data were then analyzed using a machine learning method to identify image patterns and classify land cover types. The classification results were compared with known reference points for accuracy checking, ensuring reliable identification of vegetation and other surface types.

To fulfil the co-design aims, all outcomes of this study, including vegetation indices and datasets such as orthophotomaps derived from multispectral images, were presented to the farmers managing the surveyed fields. Data and key results were visually presented as easily interpreted maps using a multilayered Geographic Information System (GIS) package to harmonise the communication styles of academia and farmers. Farmers were trained to independently interact with the GIS package in QGIS software, allowing them to provide in-depth feedback regarding the study and its applicability for grassland management.

2. Methodology

The study was conducted in 10 fields used for forage cultivation in the Ērgļi Parish, located in the Vidzeme region of Latvia. The region is known for its diverse nature, which includes clean lakes and the Ogre River, and for its landscapes and rich historical heritage, which attracts touristic activities such as boating, cycling, and trekking. The average temperature ranges from -4.5°C in January and February to 18°C in July (LVGMC, 2025). The region receives a moderate amount

of precipitation throughout the year. The wettest months are typically June, July, August, September, October, and November, with October having the highest monthly amount of rain (LVGMC, 2025). However, the Baltic region was experiencing a severe drought during the conduction of the study, in 2023's summer (EU Joint Research Centre, 2023; Via Baltica, 2023). The local flora includes a mix of deciduous and coniferous trees, such as birch, pine, and spruce. Wildflowers and grasses are abundant, contributing to the region's biodiversity and supporting its agricultural landscape. This diverse vegetation is adapted to the temperate climate and plays a key role in the region's agricultural activities, including the cultivation of legume forage crops such as red clover for livestock feeding, as well as for soil conservation (Şakiroğlu, 2021).

The flight planning, operation, and post-processing were performed using eMotion Release 3.16.0. Flights were set with an expected resolution of 10 cm/pixel, 65% lateral overlap, and 80% longitudinal overlap. The flights were planned along parallel lines with an inclination from the north-south direction, with minor on-site adjustments for wind direction before the flight to ensure consistency in image capture spacing and to reduce impairments on subsequent processing effectiveness. To ensure accuracy, we used a colour-calibration target (Airinov white-balance target) before each flight to calibrate the camera. The drone also had an onboard Global Navigation Satellite System Real-time Kinematic/Post-Processed Kinematic (GNSS RTK/PPK) receiver activated. Data recorded during the flight were post-processed using differential correction data provided by the Estonian Land Board's virtual reference stations (Metsar et al., 2018). This method produces higher horizontal and vertical accuracies than using ground control points (Tomaščík et al., 2019).

Reflectance maps created from corrected Parrot Sequoia images were used to calculate various vegetation indices. Table 1 lists and describes the specific indices employed, considering past experiences in varying applications and the suitability with Parrot Sequoia multispectral bands (e.g., Bergamo et al. 2023; de Lima et al., 2022; Li et al. 2021a, 2021b; Villoslada et al. 2020).

Table 1. Description and formulas of multispectral VIs used in this study.

Index	Equation	Application(s)	Strength(s)	Limitation(s)	Reference
Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)	$(NIR - RED) / (NIR + RED)$	Assess vegetation density and health; Agriculture; Environmental	Simplicity; Versatility	Saturation in dense vegetation; Soil effects; Atmospheric	Rouse et al. (1974)

		monitoring		interference	
Green Difference Vegetation Index (GDVI)	$NIR - GREEN$	Assess vegetation stress; Dryland characterization	Higher sensitivity to low vegetation cover; Better dynamic range	Limited use in dense vegetation; Atmospheric effects	Sripada et al. (2006)
Green Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (GNDVI)	$(NIR - GREEN) / (NIR + GREEN)$	Evaluate vegetation vigor and health; Agriculture	Enhanced sensitivity to chlorophyll content; Agricultural use	Soil background effects; Saturation in high vegetation density	Gitelson et al. (1996)
Green-Red Vegetation Index (GRVI)	$NIR / GREEN$	Assess vegetation stress; Forest canopy monitoring	High sensitivity to leaf pigments; Specificity in forest canopies	Limited use in non-forest areas; Atmospheric effects	Sripada et al. (2006)
Green Infrared Percentage Vegetation Index (GIPVI)	$NIR / (NIR + GREEN)$	Assess vegetation health and productivity; Agricultural monitoring	Sensitivity to vegetation health; Versatility	Atmospheric effects; Soil background sensitivity	Crippen (1990)
Simple Ratio (SR)	NIR / RED	Estimate vegetation health and density; Crop monitoring	Simplicity; Versatility	Saturation in dense vegetation; Soil effects	Jordan (1969)
Green Difference Index (GDI)	$NIR - RED + GREEN$	Assess vegetation stress; Chlorophyll content estimation	High sensitivity to vegetation stress; Specificity	Atmospheric effects; Soil background sensitivity	Gianelle & Vescovo (2007)
Green-Red Difference Index (GRDI)	$(GREEN - RED) / (GREEN + RED)$	Assess vegetation stress; Chlorophyll content estimation	High sensitivity to vegetation stress; Specificity	Atmospheric effects; Soil background sensitivity	Gianelle & Vescovo (2007)
Red-Edge Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI-RE)	$(NIR - REG) / (NIR + REG)$	Measure plant health; Crop monitoring	Enhanced sensitivity to chlorophyll content; Agricultural use	Soil background effects; Saturation in high vegetation density	Gitelson & Merzlyak (1994)
Red-edge simple ratio (SRRE)	NIR / REG	Estimate vegetation health and density; Crop monitoring	Simplicity; Versatility	Saturation in dense vegetation; Soil effects	Gitelson & Merzlyak (1994)

Red-Edge Triangular Vegetation Index (RTVI)	$100 * (NIR - REG) - 10 * (NIR - GREEN)$	Estimate leaf area index and biomass; Crop monitoring	High sensitivity to vegetation health; Specificity	Atmospheric effects; Soil background sensitivity	Chen et al. (2010)
Modified Simple Ratio (MSR)	$((NIR / REG) - 1) / (\sqrt{(NIR / REG) + 1})$	Assess vegetation health and reduce soil noise	Enhanced sensitivity to vegetation health; Soil noise reduction	Atmospheric effects; Complexity	Haboudane et al. (2004)
DATT4	$REG / GREEN * REG$	Assess chlorophyll content; Crop monitoring	High sensitivity to chlorophyll content; Specificity	Atmospheric effects; Soil background sensitivity	Datt (1998)

To identify and map areas covered by red clover and other vegetation types, we used the drone-based dataset and a machine learning algorithm, namely a Random Forest (RF) classifier (Breiman, 2001), to distinguish different land cover types. RF models are known for their high accuracy and robustness. By combining the predictions of multiple trees, they reduce the risk of overfitting (when a model is too closely focused on the training data and performs poorly on new data). This algorithm learns from information contained in the drone images, recognizing colour and shape patterns that help distinguish different features in the landscape. Thus, this algorithm creates multiple decision trees using different subsets of the data. Each tree is trained on a random sample of the data and makes its predictions. Once all the trees have made their predictions, the RF combines these predictions to make a final decision. Specifically for classification tasks, it uses a majority vote system, where the most common prediction among the trees is chosen as the true class.

The procedure employed follows what other researchers have done for similar applications in Estonia (e.g., Villoslada et al., 2020; Bergamo et al., 2023). Categories based on a European dataset from the European Environment Agency (Chytrý et al., 2020) were used to identify land cover classes within the drone-based maps of the sites. These classes included ‘*artificial surfaces*’, ‘*shadows*’, ‘*water*’, ‘*trees*’, ‘*bare soil*’, ‘*red clover*’, ‘*other grasses*’, and ‘*ornamental grasses*’ (as shown in Figure 1). Specifically, the class ‘*ornamental grasses*’ comprised managed grassy areas created for aesthetic or recreational purposes, showing visually uniform and regular spectral patterns (Parra et al., 2020). In contrast, “*Other grasses*” included semi-natural grasses that have developed through low-intensity traditional management practices (e.g., mowing, grazing) with the exception of ‘*Red clover*’. For training the RF classifier, we manually digitised at

least 10 points for each land cover class from the true-color orthomaps, with half assigned for validation of the results. Before training and validating the RF model, a grid-search procedure was used for tuning the hyperparameters to avoid overfitting and reduce model complexity. This procedure indicated that the best combination of parameters was $mtry = 3$, and $ntree = 500$.

Figure 1. Example of the orthomaps of one of the locations covered by the drone flight missions and the dataset used for training and validating the RF models for land cover classification within the area.

To assess the overall classification accuracy, metrics such as overall accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity were calculated. Overall accuracy represents the proportion of samples correctly classified relative to the total number of samples in the test set. Sensitivity quantifies the proportion of actual positive cases correctly identified by the model, while specificity evaluates the accuracy of the model in predicting negative cases. Class accuracy indicates the number of correctly classified instances for each distinct class, allowing for a more refined assessment of the algorithm's performance across various categories.

3. Results

Based on the reflectance maps obtained from the six drone flight missions, we were able to calculate and map the vegetation indices listed and described in Table 1. Figure 2 displays some of the indices mapped in one location, illustrating their ability to highlight diverse surfaces and features. From these maps, the points manually digitized extracted the pixel values in a radius of 15 cm to generate a dataset that was used for training and validating the classifying models.

Figure 2. Examples of the multispectral indices calculated for the land cover classification in one of the fields to illustrate their ability to describe different features in the landscape.

Concerning the training data, the RF classification model showed an overall accuracy of 87.5%. Based on the validation data, a slightly lower value was observed: 68.3%. ‘Water’ was the class with the highest classification accuracy, with 90.7%. ‘Trees’ and ‘other grasses’ had the highest error rates (>25%), with large confusion among themselves and ‘red clover’ (Figure 3). The ‘red clover’ class also showed an intermediate accuracy in the validation dataset, where 81.2% of the test pixels were correctly classified. Analyzing the other accuracy metrics, the classification model demonstrated a satisfactory performance to detect and distinguish this class from the others. The ‘red clover’ sensitivity value showed that in 71.1% of the cases, the model was able to detect this class, while the specificity value indicated that in 91.3% it was able to separate correctly it from the other classes. Table 2 displays the complete set of the accuracy metrics calculated from the application of the RF model to the validation dataset.

Actual	Water	116	0	6	0	0	15	0	4
	Trees	0	95	1	13	16	0	46	0
	Bare soil	6	0	132	0	4	9	0	25
	Shadows	0	10	6	111	7	0	16	24
	Other grasses	0	35	10	0	94	0	30	3
	Ornamental grasses	2	0	10	0	13	58	0	0
	Red Clover	0	81	1	7	50	7	359	0
	Artificial	5	3	25	0	5	2	0	104
		Water	Trees	Bare soil	Shadows	Other grasses	Ornamental grasses	Red Clover	Artificial
Predicted									

Figure 3. Confusion matrix of the classification results based on the validation dataset.

Table 2. Summary of RF model validation assessment.

	Class Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity
Water	0.907	0.823	0.991
Trees	0.731	0.555	0.907
Bare Soil	0.834	0.750	0.957
Shadows	0.811	0.638	0.985
Other grasses	0.739	0.546	0.932
Ornamental grasses	0.838	0.699	0.978
Red Clover	0.812	0.711	0.913
Artificial	0.841	0.722	0.961

After training and validating the classifier, we applied its algorithm to the maps of each field, producing the land cover maps displayed in Figure 4. Visually, it is possible to notice the confusion between ‘red clover’ and ‘trees’. In some of the fields (e.g., frames ‘d’ and ‘f’), the class ‘ornamental grasses’ is also observed in mistaken locations in a smaller magnitude. However, this could be expected due to the similarity between these plant physiognomies.

Figure 4. Final land cover maps generated with the RF classification algorithm.

Despite that, the land cover maps generated using the RF model were able to indicate the locations within the fields with a higher concentration of 'red clover', showing to be a good to for subsiding management and corrective actions to increase its cover where its presence is less dense. Figure 5 displays an example of how the 'red clover' pixels could be extracted from the land cover map and used for highlighting the areas where it occurs, allowing also the calculation of its fractional coverage in the fields.

Figure 5. Example of the red clover map (red pixels) extracted from the land cover outcome generated with the Random Forest classification model using multispectral drone images. a) displays the raw orthomosaic, and b) the 'red clover' coverage overlapping the orthomosaic.

4. Considerations and recommendations

Furthermore, the RF classification models were shown to be powerful tools for analysing complex datasets and making accurate predictions. Their ability to handle large amounts of data and identify important features makes them particularly useful in agriculture and environmental monitoring. In this way, both the land cover maps and, specifically, the 'red clover' distribution maps were shown to provide meaningful contributions to the landowners about future directions on crop management. The study's core findings, for example, Figure 6, informed farmers' decision-making regarding the future management of the surveyed fields: the greater the percentage of red clover coverage, the more productive the field is likely to be in producing livestock feed. Red clover was reseeded in these fields in the following season using drone technology (outside the scope of this paper). The areas with a lower percentage of red clover underwent additional analysis by the farmer and farm advisors to assess their eligibility for EU valuable semi-natural grassland habitat restoration (Rūsiņa, 2017); consequently, one field was determined to be eligible.

Figure 6. Example of core results: a map of the red clover coverage within the boundaries of one of the study fields with a percentage indicator.

Yet, training algorithms using automated methods for algorithm comparison and tuning, such as the AutoML modules in Python (Li et al., 2021b) could obtain improved classification models. In this example, the authors were able to distinguish multiple agricultural management practices related to soil tillage methods, cultivation methods, and nutrient application. From this perspective, this approach seems to be a promising alternative for selecting, training and optimizing machine learning algorithms for farm mapping efforts. Thus, enhanced digital products could be generated and even replicated in other locations and contexts.

The unexpected outcome of the co-design approach was that not only the core results but also all the data generated during the drone-based remote sensing methodology, such as orthophotomaps derived from multispectral images, were relevant to farmers' decision-making and future management planning of the surveyed fields. From the farmers' perspective, products such as orthomaps (figure 5) and land cover maps (figure 4), can serve as a valuable tool for farmland management planning and provide a comprehensive GIS record of changes in grasslands, which can be retrospectively analysed as historical documentation of agricultural landscape development.

It is also essential to provide all study data as a GIS package that facilitates interactivity and to obtain comprehensive feedback from farmers to understand the full potential of the multispectral survey's applications in grassland management.

5. Challenges and limitations

The results showed some limitations in distinguishing red clover from trees using multispectral images, likely due to similar spectral signatures. To overcome this case specifically, an alternative for enhancing the separation could involve including tri-dimensional models in the RF models. This type of metric was previously shown to improve the discrimination of diverse vegetation types, using mainly the plant height for this (e.g., Kattenborn et al., 2019; Lopatin et al., 2019; de Lima et al., 2022; Bergamo et al., 2023). However, this solution would depend on the availability of an additional sensor to collect true colour photographs that could be used in Structure-from-Motion workflows, which usually depend on commercially licensed software.

Due to an equipment malfunction, the geolocation of field measurements of red-clover coverage could not be used in the modelling procedure, limiting our possibilities to explore the application of the drone images for precise quantification of the actual coverage of this plant species. In remote sensing modelling, it is widely acknowledged that the incorporation of larger ground truth samples is beneficial to these efforts, allowing retrieving more accurate algorithms (Wu et al., 2023). In such a way, future efforts should focus on ensuring all the required information for appropriately executing the co-designed experiments, the necessary data are effectively collected and the objectives of the applications are tailored to the needs of all the people involved and institutions.

6. Acknowledgements

This research was funded by the Horizon Europe project CODECS – maximising the CO-benefits of agricultural digitalisation through conducive digital ECoSystems (101060179 - CODECS - HORIZON-CL6-2021- GOVERNANCE-01) and the Chair of Environmental Protection and Landscape Management, Estonian University of Life Sciences. Vineta Gailite contributed to the research as CODECS LivingLab’s coordinator, facilitating the co-design process of the study and communications between farmers and researcher.

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